

A IS CORRECT OF THE INTEGRAL TO THE ECONOMY APPLICATIONS

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ANNOTATION.

In the article economic processes image to do and of them other , economic indicators in the calculation use , income and cost concept and to them about integrals count studied. This , the economy analysis make , income and expenses manage for is used .

Key words: labor productivity of production, stock of products (goods), volume of product production, income function,

ANNOTATION.

In the article, the description of economic processes and their use in calculating other economic indicators, the concept of income and expenses and the calculation of their integrals are studied. This is used for the analysis of the economy, management of income and expenses.

Enter

Definite integral, finance calculation in the field , for example , calculation perform and financial essence in the calculation done will be increased. Economic models and algorithms in making is used . It is economical processes image to do and of them other , for example , economic indicators in the calculation used will be. Exact integral, income and cost concept and to them about integrals in the calculation is used . This is the economy analysis make , income and expenses manage for applied. Investment activity and expenses , income , profit , loss , income increase and reduction , investment portfolio make up such as concepts in the calculation is used . Economical integral concepts in the field , costs and trade policy the problem analysis in doing is used . Trade policy and financial strategies in defining of the integral role important _

These examples are clear of the integral in economics how application to be done show important _ From integral mathematics come came out concept in the economy created in models , events and in strategies done is increased .

It is known that labor productivity the work day during variable is the amount . Labor productivity $y = f(x)$ function with be expressed in this x the work of the day from the beginning calculated time range , $f(x)$ while of time

that's it current labor $\dots$ productivity means $\dots$ Labor of productivity the work volume in the 4th hour of the day count issue placed let it be

Time interval (3,4). the most of the elder length Δx has been to intervals we will be and $f(x)$ function this small in intervals immutable let's say work release work productivity $f(x) \Delta x$ to multiplication equal to will be So work $\dots$ work in the 4th hour of the day release work productivity

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \sum_3^4 f(x) \Delta x = \int_3^4 f(x) dx$$

equality with is expressed .

Products to the warehouse time together to be brought product the amount $f(x)$ and product to the warehouse come from falling started time unit x if $\dots x$ from $x + \Delta x$ time between to the warehouse $f(x) \Delta x$ unity product will come . So , to the warehouse product continuously come if he stands , in him of the goods reserve

$$\int_0^x f(x) dx$$

with is expressed .

Mechanical engineering industry something kind of machine tools work emits and yearly work release immutable a to equal to being $\dots x$ that's it machine tools work issued years let it be

will be If the product work release volume arithmetic progression according to grower ie

$$f(x) = a_0 + a_1 x$$

if , lathes the number

$$\int_0^t (a_0 + a_1 x) dx = \left[a_0 x + \frac{a_1 x^2}{2} \right]_0^t = a_0 t + \frac{a_1 t^2}{2}$$

organize is enough

Yearly income of time t function $D = f(x)$ let it be Percent (percent) rate share i is , interest on top of it adding continuously is considered Your income t per year calculated discount find the volume . The end of the discount total with funds $\dots$ initial between funds $\dots$ to the difference it is said .

This amount count for , time range t the n equal to into pieces we separate . of time too small $\dots \Delta t$ between income as $f(t) \Delta t$ immutable to equal

to by doing get can _ Continuously on top of it adding calculated in percentages discount income as follows is :

$$\frac{f(t)\Delta t}{e^{it}} = f(t)\Delta te^{-it}.$$

(0, t) time between discount income quantity

$$\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \sum_0^t f(t)e^{-it} \Delta t = \int_0^t f(t)e^{-it} dt$$

will be

Private without , annual income immutable if , that is $f(x) = a$ if so , with a discount income

$$d = \int_0^t ae^{-it} dt = a \int_0^t fe^{-it} dt = a \left[-\frac{1}{i} e^{-it} \right]_0^t = \frac{a}{i} (1 - e^{-it})$$

will be

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